

THE IMPORTANCE OF AI IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: Today, artificial intelligence is developing at an unprecedented pace and covers almost all areas, including education. This article discusses the advantages of using AI (Artificial Intelligence) in education, its positive impact on the quality of education, its ability to organize the educational process qualitatively and create many conveniences in the educational process.

Keywords: AI, artificial intelligence, individual learning, educational algorithms, innovative education, intensive training program

Special attention is paid to the education of the younger generation on a global scale. Work is being carried out consistently to create the necessary conditions for young people to receive modern knowledge and grow up with high spirituality. By the 21st century, science has developed to such an extent that it has become impossible to imagine a single day of our lives without scientific achievements and technologies. In particular, concepts such as an information society and artificial intelligence have become a fundamental part of our lives. If we touch on the concept of artificial intelligence, which is often encountered in our society, first of all, we need to understand the concept of intelligence. The work being carried out in our country to improve all parts of the education system - preschool education, school, secondary specialized and higher education, to build new institutions and renovate existing ones. Artificial intelligence is a rapidly developing field of technology that is concerned with creating intelligent machines that can mimic human behavior and perform tasks with human-like accuracy. The field of artificial intelligence focuses on creating software and systems that can learn from data, reason, understand natural language, perceive images and sounds, and make decisions based on information collected through various means. That is why it is so important in our lives. On the other hand, artificial intelligence is not a new concept to us. Fantasy works such as Mary Shelley's science fiction masterpiece Frankenstein and Fritz Lang's classic film Metropolis have also captured the desire to create beings that can perform human-like functions. (Z. O.

Nurmatov, O. N. Chorshamiyeva, F. A. Pirimova "Ta'limda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari").

We are living in a time of rapidly developing globalization. Naturally, this requires the formation of modern thinking and a modern worldview and the use of modern innovative technologies. We cannot imagine our modern life without modern technologies, and they cover all aspects of our lives. In particular, they have had an impact on the education sector. Technologies and applications in education are rapidly being updated and expanded. In addition, the continuous development of smart products brings great convenience and innovations to people's study, work and life. In recent years, attention has been increasingly focused on providing the younger generation with quality education. By the 21st century, science has developed to such an extent that it is impossible to imagine a single day without scientific achievements and technologies. In particular, concepts such as information society and artificial intelligence have become an integral part of our lives. The term AI (English: Artificial Intelligence) is often found in our daily lives, and its application is developing all over the world. Recently, artificial intelligence has been introduced into various networks and social infrastructures. Today, artificial intelligence (AI) is intensively taking its place in the field of education. AI plays a major role in creating information systems that have the ability to learn, analyze, transform and visualize data. These systems help in performing tasks such as searching for information for specific purposes, analyzing data, and displaying results during the learning process.

Compared to natural and human capabilities, artificial intelligence (AI) brings several benefits to the field of education. This article highlights several useful aspects of artificial intelligence in the field of education. First of all, AI has had a significant impact on saving the learner's time and successful development in education. The capabilities of AI are wide-ranging, it can answer questions of interest to you, draw pictures on command or create presentations on various topics, and even write various abstracts and articles. AI helps students to self-manage, and analyze their individual learning methods. Its educational algorithms are adapted based on the individual characteristics and learning methods of students, which increases the abilities of each student in his or her own educational path. It also provides the student with the opportunity to learn independently. Based on the knowledge levels, interests, weaknesses and characteristics of students in the process of learning, AI adapts educational programs and allows each student to get the best results in the acquired educational path. AI helps in assessing the information of students and specific planning for it. Based on the characteristics of the student, the formation of the

knowledge level and the interests of students, AI allows for the specialization of educational programs and specific recommendations.

Artificial intelligence creates many conveniences not only for students, but also for teachers in the process of teaching. For example, in order to create an intensive educational program and organize the lesson according to it more interesting and meaningful, the teacher can use various methods with the help of AI to study topics of interest to students and increase the ability to find, analyze and explain information about them, various fields can be studied, such as genetics, robotics, demonstrative learning, natural language learning, etc. With the help of applications and applications in artificial intelligence, teachers can help assess students, create educational programs, learn words, sentences and mathematical problems. By using these applications, the interactivity and intensity of education is increased. Benefits of using artificial intelligence in education:

- Helping to further improve the quality of education by saving students and teachers' time
- Increasing the level of student mastery
- The ability for teachers to create new methods using AI and use them in the educational process
- Using various animations and visual aids
- Organizing the lesson process based on students' interests.
- It creates many advantages, such as increasing the student's individual learning potential and helping to consolidate the knowledge learned.

(Sh. O. Mamayoqubova, N. Zubaydova, Abduvaxidov Begali Nurali o'g'li – "ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA SUN'IY INTELLEKTDAN FOYDALANISH")

Conclusion:

In conclusion, artificial intelligence effectively helps students and teachers use innovative teaching methods, develop educational materials, individual practice experiences and improve the quality of education.

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